

CEDA Annual Report 24-25

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Introduction

PHIL KERSHAW, HEAD OF CEDA

This year marks an important milestone as we celebrate 30 years of CEDA! Starting with a team of just three people in 1994, we have grown to nearly 40 staff members in 2025. Alongside the articles describing our work over the last year, we have included a special feature to take in the bigger picture, looking back over our history and development to where we are today.

In November 2024, [we hosted a birthday](#) celebration to mark the occasion. We met with friends and colleagues in RAL Space, more widely in STFC and with our funders and stakeholders. As I prepared my presentation for the event, it struck me the vast transformation in technologies employed over the 30 years, the contributions made by team members and leaders past and present and the support of our partners and sponsors that has made possible some key innovations. Some highlights for me: in the early 2000s, the e-Science programme helped towards the development of the NERC DataGrid, a series of projects which laid groundwork for services to federate and interconnect data centres both nationally and internationally. Then moving forward to 2012 and the creation of JASMIN, a first of its kind data intensive supercomputer dedicated for the environmental sciences.

To undertake this diverse portfolio of work, we must also have a continued diverse stream of funding income, without which it would not be possible to support the diverse technical work undertaken by our expert team. This includes, but is not limited to UK Research and Innovation's (UKRI) Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), via the research centres, National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) and National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO), UK Met Office, Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA), Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT), European Commission, UK Space Agency (UKSA), European Space Agency (ESA) and UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure.

We hope this report will share with you the diversity, impact and importance of our work supporting environmental research over the last three decades which will hopefully continue for many years to come!

About CEDA

The Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) is based in the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)'s RAL Space department. CEDA operates data centres and delivers data infrastructure, primarily for the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), and undertakes project work for a range of national and international funders. CEDA's mission is to provide data and information services for environmental science: this includes curation of scientifically important environmental data for the long term, and facilitation of the use of data by the environmental science community.

CEDA ARCHIVE

CEDA Archive was established in 2005, as a merged entity incorporating two NERC designated data centres: the British Atmospheric Data Centre, and the NERC Earth Observation Data Centre. Since April 2018, the CEDA Archive has been a component part of the NERC Environmental Data Service, which brings together the five NERC data centres into a single service commissioned by NERC as National Capability.

JASMIN

JASMIN is the data intensive supercomputer which provides the infrastructure upon which the CEDA archives and services are delivered. Increasingly, JASMIN provides flexible data analysis capabilities to a growing community, who benefit from high performance compute and a private cloud, co-located with petascale data storage.

Team discussion at the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis

The CEDA team

We have had several new staff members join CEDA in the last year. In September 2024 we welcomed Matthew Paice from BGS as both a Data Scientist and Software Engineer. We gained 2 new graduates on the STFC graduate scheme: Danny Lloyd (Research Computing Service Support) and Adrian Dębski (Software Engineer).

We also had two Industrial Placement students join us for the academic year, Ed Borthwick and Stanislav Tyshkovets. We welcomed RAL Space graduate Ioana Circu, who joined us for 6 weeks to undertake a software development placement. We also had Yufan Kambang, Rowan Moss, and William Cross join for part of the year as apprentice software engineers.

Four members of our team who joined 2+ years ago also came to the end of their graduate scheme. Congratulations to Daniel Westwood, Nicola Farmer, Molly MacRae, and Emily Anderson for completing the graduate scheme!

We unfortunately said goodbye to Suresh Balaji, who has moved back to RAL Space to continue project management.

Meet the team

Adrian Dębski
Graduate Software Engineer

Adrian Hines
Director of JASMIN

Ag Stephens
Head of Partnerships

Alan Iwi
Senior Software Engineer

Alex Manning
Research Software Engineer / Operations Support for JASMIN

Alison Pamment
Data Scientist: Metadata Standards

Alison Waterfall
Senior Data Scientist: Earth Observation

Andrew Harwood
Infrastructure Manager

Chaminuka Mbanje
JASMIN Storage and User Support

Charlotte Pascoe
Senior Data Scientist: Models

Daniel Westwood
Software Engineer

Danny Lloyd
Graduate Research Computing Service Support

Dave Poulter
Technical Manager

Diane Knappett
Senior Data Scientist - Earth Observation

Ed Williamson
Data Scientist: Earth Observation

Ellie Fisher
Graduate Data Scientist

Emily Anderson
Environmental Data Scientist

Esther Conway
Senior Data Scientist:
Earth Observation

Fatima Chami
JASMIN User Support

Federica Moscato
Head of Earth Observation

Graham Parton
Data Management Specialist

Hayley Gray
User Support and Metadata Services Operator

Jennifer Bulpett
Senior Project Manager

Jesse Alexander
Scientific Programming and Outreach Graduate

Martin Juckes
Head of Atmospheric Science and Research and deputy head of CEDA

Matt Jones
Senior DevOps Engineer

Matt Pritchard
JASMIN Operations Manager

Matthew Paice
Data Scientist & Software Developer

Matthew Wild
Senior Data Scientist: UKSSDC

Molly MacRae
Environmental Data Scientist

Neil Massey
Senior Software Engineer

Nicola Farmer
Software Engineer

Phil Kershaw
Head of CEDA

Poppy Townsend
Communications Manager

Rhys Evans
Software Engineer

Sam Pepler
Head of Curation

Steve Donegan
Senior Data Scientist: Earth Observation

Wendy Garland
Senior Data Scientist: Aircraft

William Tucker
Software Engineer

Celebrating 30 years of the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis

In November 2024, [we hosted an event](#) to celebrate 30 years of CEDA where we looked back at the contributions of the team past and present and shared our current work and future mission.

To mark the occasion, CEDA staff member, Molly MacRae, created [“The Land of CEDA” artwork](#) – a map to give a light-hearted view of our organisation as an island together with the different aspects of our work, represented as landmarks and features. Other organisations we work closely with are only a short voyage away!

A medieval-style map showcasing an island: The Land of CEDA with geographical features related to our domain areas such as ‘the Kingdom of JASMIN’ or ‘Open Data Plains’. The island also has ocean routes leading towards other organisations that we work with like the ‘RAL Space realm’ or the ‘Scientific Computing Court’

This varied landscape is only possible due to the iterative and innovative work undertaken by dedicated staff over the years. It is the people who have made it all possible: our experts are essential for designing, improving and maintaining a vast number of data and compute services. This year, we are leading the data management for over 300 active projects, facilitating access to 400+ group workspaces to enable data sharing and analysis, and are involved in 13 large collaborative projects. Many of these projects are in an international and world-leading setting, testament to a huge growth from the first single [project supported by our work](#) 30 years ago. Increasingly we are supporting individuals who sit outside of our core remit communities, researchers within the atmosphere, earth observation, and solar and space physics domains. In the last five years, we've received over 40,000 new user registrations for access to data, and over 2000 researchers actively rely on our services for data analysis and collaborative research. For the majority of these users, we will never interact with them directly or understand their data or compute needs due to the trend towards open data and thus anonymous access. Where we do have metrics on usage, we can see examples including: engineering, economics, health or personal interest.

Additionally, data volumes have grown vastly; the Archive now holds over 26 petabytes of data. Earth observation data, which was originally stored in a box under a desk(!), now makes up approximately 80% (over 22 petabytes of data) of our long term archive. Our capacity to collaboratively store and analyse data has also increased. Our computing infrastructure, JASMIN, now has over 60 petabytes of disk and solid state storage and 90 petabytes of tape; making JASMIN's initial 4.5 petabytes of storage in 2012 seem minuscule by comparison.

Technical advances have also enabled our services to be more resilient and efficient. We continue to experiment with innovative research projects at the forefront of new technologies, whilst also ensuring security and reliability are at the heart of our operations. We have combined the requirement to upgrade the operating system across our fleet of more than one hundred services with a drive to upgrade these services to more modern methods of containerised deployment wherever this is possible.

To support this ever-evolving complex landscape of work, this year we have refreshed our mission and strategic themes.

OUR MISSION:

- To deliver innovative Atmospheric & Earth Observation data services for the benefit of science and society

OUR STRATEGIC THEMES:

- Nurture & develop the talent of our people through constant improvement
- Findable, accessible, interoperable & reusable (FAIR data principles)
- Increase inter-agency collaboration
- Lead the bridging between Earth Observation & climate data
- Focus on user centricity
- Co-location of compute and data
- Provision of training and sharing expertise to serve the wider community
- Run TRUSTed (Transparent, Responsible, User-focused, Sustainable & Technology) data centric NERC facilities

OUR PROGRAMMES OF WORK:

- Atmospheric Science – providing tools, services & expertise that support Atmospheric scientists to share and analyse data
- Earth Observation – provide access to standardised Earth Observation data & Essential Climate Variables at both national and international levels
- Environmental Data Service – a trusted UK facility providing data stewardship services ensuring environmental data of long-term value are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (includes CEDA Archive & others)
- JASMIN – meet the needs of the environmental science community for storing data and working with it. Provide host infrastructure for the CEDA Archive with data analysis platform alongside

Seven key themes were identified to showcase the breadth of work and expertise covered by our team – spanning all of our programmes of work and strategic themes. This report is also structured around these themes, highlighting key activities undertaken during 2024/25:

Curate – Curation and data archival

Connect – Community engagement and support

Relate & Facilitate – Internal relationships & external stakeholders

Net Zero – Sustainable storage and computing

Technical – Tools, expertise and infrastructure

Co-create – User centred design, co-creation and collaboration

Outreach – Public engagement and education

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Key events timeline:

Celebrating 30 years!

The entire CEDA department stood behind the warming stripes mosaic at the CEDA 30th birthday celebration event

Curate

Curation and data archival

Curate

Curation and data archival

POPPY TOWNSEND

What is the CEDA Archive?

The CEDA Archive is the national data centre for atmospheric and earth observation data and forms part of [NERC’s Environmental Data Service](#) - a network of data centres covering all aspects of environmental science.

We curate data covering climate, atmospheric composition, model simulations and numerical weather prediction as well as various earth observation datasets, including airborne and satellite data and imagery. Our main goal is to ensure that atmospheric and earth observation data are made available and accessible to all in order to fully realise their reuse potential.

What’s in our Archive?

Infographic depicting a pie chart showing what proportion of the 30+PB of data in the CEDA Archive is taken up by which datasets and how large they are:

How do we get our data?

Infographic showcasing the CEDA Data Life Cycle - a cyclical process involving the steps below:

Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
 SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
 NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

All stats shown are for Apr 2024 – 25

Transforming climate data services with Agile project delivery

DIANE KNAPPETT, FEDE MOSCATO, ALISON WATERFALL, EMILY ANDERSON, ELLIE FISHER

CEDA has been part of ESA's Climate Change Initiative (CCI) Knowledge Exchange (KE) project since 2015, archiving CCI datasets and publishing them via the CCI Open Data Portal (ODP) - see: <https://climate.esa.int/en/data/#/dashboard>. The latest phase of the project, Climate Space, kicked off in October 2024, and involves a significant number of new technical developments, in addition to expanding the CEDA CCI ODP team's core activities. As a result, the team expanded, and it became evident that a new approach was needed to manage the project's ambitious number of requirements effectively. This came at a time when the wider RAL Space department was embarking on a dedicated Continuous Improvement (CI) programme. This gave the team the opportunity to participate and enlist the help of Noel Warnell from NOW Agile Ltd, on a 6-month CI coaching activity to help them implement an "Agile" approach to project management.

The CCI ODP team's CI journey began with a thorough project retrospective, which involved mapping out the timeline of CEDA's involvement in the CCI KE project and reflecting on what approaches had been successful as well as areas that needed improvement. Having someone external to lead this activity was valuable as they were able to provide a fresh perspective on the team's existing approach. The team focused on mapping out the CCI data archival pipeline, providing estimates of the time taken per task involved and, crucially, adding estimated wait times between tasks. It was surprising to realise that wait time – often waiting for a decision to be made internally, or for a response from a third party – far outstripped actual work time, slowing the archival pipeline down significantly. In some cases, datasets could take over 90 days to pass through the pipeline from start to finish. The team identified several pinch points in the archival process, e.g. manual file metadata checks, and then identified solutions to improve efficiency, e.g. by writing software to automate file checking. A project Kanban board was also set up containing tickets for both project requirements and CI efficiency tasks in order to easily keep track of progress.

Jon Robson with illuminated globe
© National Centre for Atmospheric Science

Following the initial CI retrospective and forward planning session, the CCI ODP team established a weekly team meeting to touch base and review the project Kanban board tickets, report on progress, and flag any issues encountered. They also used monthly Agile ‘sprints’, which began with a planning meeting to map out the work for the month and ended with a retrospective session to identify lessons learned.

Across the 6 months of Continuous Improvement (CI) coaching, members of the team progressively took on greater responsibility for CI activities, such as leading weekly/monthly meetings, so that by the end of the coaching period the team was self-managing. Now, almost 9 months into the project, the team can look back and reflect on how their use of CI has developed: the project Kanban board has now evolved into a set of SMART tasks, each with an assigned lead, giving individuals ownership of tasks and ensuring that no tasks slip off the radar. The team has also now struck a better balance between required tasks and improvement activities; the team has started reviewing tasks in order of priority to ensure that urgent and important tasks (e.g. requirements for upcoming deliverables) are always addressed before spending time on less urgent improvement measures. Furthermore, giving tasks a named lead has helped spread the project workload and given team members both valuable experience and a strong sense of achievement when completing assigned tasks.

Implementing CI has helped the growing CCI ODP team address the large number of project requirements in a systematic way and led to greater efficiency; the lead time for data archival has been significantly reduced, improving delivery speed and reducing the cost to archive each dataset. The project has also seen an increase in the quantity of data being processed and the team is implementing various additional data archival pipeline updates that will improve efficiency further. Thinking more broadly for CEDA, aspects of Agile have been applied for some time on software development projects. What is new and unique however is its application for our data processing and operations. Going forwards, the CCI ODP team will continue with the CI mindset in this project as well as incorporating and revisiting elements of the Agile methodology that have been found to work well in other projects across CEDA.

Ellie Fisher, Graduate Data Scientist

“ Having joined the CCI KE team in early 2024, I feel that working with Agile has really benefited how we work together and the insight that I as an individual have into what others in the team are working on. There is a strong sense of wanting everybody to be informed and actively involved, and a drive to make things better!”

Seamless sensor data streams: making the data flow and ready to go

GRAHAM PARTON, WENDY GARLAND

Operational sensor networks are often well organised to feed regular measurements into their specific, individual data systems, but research instrumentation often needs to be operated differently. The nuances and care needed for research-grade use can result in complex data production and flows, plus the requirement to convey details to end-users, both now and into the future, to ensure good science follows. However, this can lead to administrative and technical burdens that can hamper data flows and hinder re-use. Instrument operators, such as those within [the National Centre for Atmospheric Science \(NCAS\)](#), want their data to be as Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (or FAIR) as possible to ensure the greatest science and societal impact can be drawn from their measurements.

When streamlined operational networks aren't an option for research grade instrument data - which are often targeted, and bespoke observations - new approaches need to be adopted. This has been explored in the NCAS Data Activity over the past number of years and in which CEDA has been an active partner. Our approach addresses the needs of all the parties throughout the data lifecycle - from initial collection, through to curation and on to end-use, with the support for tools for production, checking and exploitation.

The initial work was to break down language barriers between those involved, collaborating to define common Data Standards. This allows workflows to be constructed to capture raw data from instruments and deliver it through to a central location in CEDA's JASMIN system, where they are backed-up and processed by the instrument scientists. Supporting contextual information (e.g. instrument details, calibrations, processing software) is captured and included throughout, and compliance-checking tools ensure that complete, formatted, archive-ready data make their way along the data pipeline into the CEDA archives where they are then published with DOIs.

It has not been a straightforward process, with refinements to the workflows and standards being needed as we've moved from planning to operationalising these approaches. However, we're moving increasingly more data through these workflows and seeing an increase in NCAS instrument data being cited in articles. This allows credit to be given to those who put in the hard work setting up and operating these instruments for their role enabling scientific progress.

The NCAS Data Activity currently supports surface, remote sensing instrumentation and imagery (including data plots) data types following common standards and workflows, but is by no means finished! It continues to develop the existing standards and include new ones covering aircraft data and laboratory measurements. It is also being adopted more widely beyond NCAS with several other community initiatives adopting the same standards and learning from our experiences.

An example of where this process has been operational is the recent Wessex convection experiment - [Observing the Evolving Structures of Turbulence \(WOEST\)](#) measurement campaign using many of the NCAS AMOF instruments. Meanwhile, the production of multiple datasets from the NCAS wind profiler instruments covering its historical deployments has enabled its data to be included within a recent publication covering a large cohort of historical, long-term products from the Met Office's Cardington Research Unit. Finally, ongoing data feeds along this data pipeline are seen with the [NCAS Sonic Anemometer deployed at the NCAS Cape Verde Atmospheric Observatory](#).

Connect

Community engagement
and support

Connect

Community engagement and support

How do we engage with our communities?

We share our expertise, skills, and resources to many environmental and technical circles both in the UK and internationally. Recent examples include:

- Invited to be a panel speaker at an international conference for digital preservation (iPRES24 in Belgium)
- Presented work on uncertainty communication at a climate event in Venice
- Remote attendance at the Research Data Alliance plenary in Costa Rica
- Advisory session with the NHS on green metrics for their IT landscape
- Meeting with the Scottish Government about how they can use our services

How do we support our communities?

One of the key ways we support the community is via our helpdesk - last year we resolved over 5510 helpdesk queries (covering both CEDA Archive and JASMIN services). We also have over 140 help documents to support users.

We also run various training events and workshops. Over 280 people were supported via CEDA led activities last year.

Introduction to JASMIN workshop example:

We provided bespoke support to 25 students in the Intelligent Earth Centre for Doctoral Training (Oxford University) cohort on 24th October 2024.

Examples of our international contributions

We contribute to the [Climate and Forecast \(CF\) standard names and metadata conventions](#), which serve the atmospheric science and modelling community among other expanding domains. Members of our team were awarded the AGU Open Science Recognition Prize in 2024.

The [Coupled Model Intercomparison Project \(CMIP\)](#) is an international climate modelling project run by the World Climate Research Program (WCRP), with the goal of understanding the similarities and differences between climate models. It has been running for 20 years through multiple phases, and with CMIP6 coming to the end, plans for CMIP7 have begun. The [Earth System Grid Federation \(ESGF\)](#) is a globally federated data infrastructure that was created to support the storage and access of the petascale data produced first for CMIP5,

Dhirendra Kumar at meteorology station

but also subsequent CMIP iterations. Staff members in CEDA are fundamental to these initiatives, providing leadership and expertise in data science, informatics, and software engineering.

Embed us in your community

Involving CEDA staff in your project or team meetings can give us a better understanding of your work and help you understand how we can support your projects. Here are some ideas that we could explore together:

- Adopt a data scientist – bring a data scientist back to meet your team and help tackle your data-related issues.
- Our graduates have a 3-month placement opportunity to broaden their experience. Do you have an idea for this kind of opportunity in your community?
- How do you see us contributing to your community? Maybe we could provide training? We're open to suggestions.

Community building - placements

Many of our staff undergo placements at other organisations, which provide great opportunities for building closer connections, knowledge sharing and learning new skills.

Examples past and present include:

William Tucker
ISIS Computing

Worked on the user front-end authentication for ISIS beamline scientists and back-end database software

Ed Williamson
Plymouth Marine Laboratory

Helped build a database of available Air-Sea Rescue Flights at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory

Dan Westwood
NCAS-CMS

Worked on an XArray implementation for Climate Forecast Aggregations with NCAS Computational Modelling Services

Poppy Townsend
FAAM

Research detachment focusing on post-flight data validation and quality control to improve the flow of data back to CEDA

Molly MacRae
NCAS, University of Reading

Research placement exploring the impacts of future aerosol legislation on European climate extremes

Emily Anderson
RAL Space

Worked in the Imaging Systems Project Management Group managing project HARMONI

Nicola Farmer
Scientific Computing

Enhancing a GUI to look at protein structures with the Collaborative Computational Project in Electron Microscopy

Martin Jukes
University of Oxford

Secondment in the Atmospheric, Oceanic and Planetary Physics department

WIP and CMIP7

CHARLOTTE PASCOE

In 2024, Charlotte Pascoe, who co-leads CEDA’s atmospheric science activities, joined the global team that makes up the [Working Group on Coupled Modelling Infrastructure Panel](#) (also known as the WIP). She shares her experience below:

The WIP is the central decision-making body for coordinating CMIP data infrastructure activities. My role on the WIP is to have oversight of the data requirements of the scientific community, including those groups focusing on climate change impacts and risks. This position also needs to take into account the capabilities of climate modelling centres and the costs of data production, storage and distribution. It serves as a bridge that joins together the science and infrastructure wings of CMIP.

The role builds on my work with Climateurope2 developing standards for climate services, the CMIP7 Data Request task team where I am the liaison for climate change Impacts and Adaptation, and my coordination role for CMIP7 planning at CEDA.

The WIP is part of the WCRP Earth System Modelling and Observations (ESMO) Core Project which was formed to coordinate all modelling, data, and observations activities across the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) and its key partners. The WIP is a Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM) panel charged with coordinating infrastructure support for CMIP and with providing guidance and feedback on other non-CMIP activities, within the interests of the WGCM, and as resources allow. This coordination role includes interaction with infrastructure delivery partners, ensuring that the technical requirements of infrastructure contributors to meet CMIP project infrastructure delivery are met.

In the CMIP7 Data Request task team I had responsibility for the climate change impacts and adaptation (I&A) research community. My impacts and adaptation (I&A) role supported a diverse group of researchers representing a wide breadth of research from energy system modelling to fisheries. I&A research is interdisciplinary in nature and the data request for this group is a harmonisation of the requirements from people working within and across different systems of knowledge. Novel methods needed to capture and harmonise the requirements from this diverse community.

I have been involved with the challenge of model documentation to a greater or lesser extent for nearly my whole career. I have seen it through various information management strategies from using NumSim to document the Met Office Unified Model, through the design of the Common Information Model (CIM) in the Metafor project, and more recently ES-DOC with whom I worked to capture the CIM experiment descriptions for CMIP6. The perspective that I gained in the Data Request team, particularly in my work embedded in the Impacts and Adaptation theme, could prove to be very useful in terms of widening the applicability and relevance of our model documentation efforts.

Charlotte Pascoe, Senior Data Scientist: Models

“ The perspective that I gained in the Data Request team, particularly in my work embedded in the Impacts and Adaptation theme, could prove to be very useful in terms of widening the applicability and relevance of our model documentation efforts.”

Supporting the ESA BIOMASS mission at CEDA

ESTHER CONWAY

The European Space Agency successfully launched the [BIOMASS satellite](#) on 29th April 2025. Carrying a novel P-band synthetic aperture radar, the Biomass mission is designed to deliver crucial information about the state of our forests and how they are changing, and to further our knowledge of the role forests play in the carbon cycle.

At CEDA we have been working closely with our NCEO colleagues on a number of projects to develop collections of ground validation data for the BIOMASS mission since 2013. These projects have connected teams of scientists in Peru, Brazil, French Guiana, USA, UK, Gabon, Ghana, Malaysia and Australia.

Weighing trees with lasers project: Terrestrial Laser Scanner data collection

This dataset collection is comprised of raw data from the NERC-funded, full waveform terrestrial laser scanner (TLS) deployed at sites spanning three continents, across multiple countries and plot locations which have been re-surveyed at different times. The terrestrial laser scanner (TLS) was able to scan thousands of trees in tropical forests in areas including Amazonia, the Congo Basin and South East Asia.

The laser data measured 3D tree volume and biomass non-destructively to within a few percent of the best current estimates (made by destructive harvesting and weighing).

Computer-generated image of ESA's BIOMASS satellite in space.
©ESA/ATG medialab

ForestScan Collection

This collection is part of the European Space Agency (ESA) funded ForestScan project, which is designed to improve the use of new Earth Observation (EO) estimates of above ground biomass (AGB) by providing terrestrial laser (TLS), unmanned airborne vehicles (UAV-LS) and airborne LiDAR (ALS) scanning-derived AGB and tree census data to compare to allometric and EO-derived estimates.

Forest Degradation Experiment (FODEX)

The FODEX project provides the first experimental arrays of biomass change plots. In total, 52 large plots will be located in logging concessions in Gabon and Peru, where biomass will be assessed before and after logging, and during recovery. In addition to traditional field inventory, terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) data will give the precise 3D shape of thousands of trees before and after disturbance, allowing biomass change to be estimated without bias.

Understanding tree architecture, form and function in the tropics

Understanding the variation in structure and form of trees is important in order to link tree physiology to tree performance, scale fluxes of water and carbon within and among trees, and understand constraints on tree growth and mortality. This project used 3D terrestrial laser scanning technologies (TLS) in combination with recently developed theoretical frameworks to measure and compare tree architecture.

To read more on the exciting science behind these data, read [Mat Disney's Blog](#), who was the NCEO PI behind many of these projects.

Relate & Facilitate

Internal relationships
& external stakeholders

Relate & Facilitate

Internal relationships & external stakeholders

Our expertise spans across multiple domains and has collaboration at its core. These include:

- Environmental science - Earth observation, atmospheric science, climate modelling
- Data standards, data services, data analysis infrastructures
- Software and tools, technical innovation, sustainable computing
- Community building, user support, project management

This means we have spent the last 30 years building a network of collaborative relationships, both internally (in our host organisations) and externally (with the global research community). The goals we're working towards in this area include:

- Bridge building between organisations
- A platform that enables collaboration between different communities
- A well-connected environmental data landscape

Internal relationships

Our overarching host organisation is [UK Research and Innovation \(UKRI\)](#) - a non-departmental public body sponsored by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT). UKRI brings together seven disciplinary research councils - we work across two of the councils; the [Science and Technology Facilities Council \(STFC\)](#) and the [Natural Environment Research Council \(NERC\)](#).

How we fit into UKRI...

- Mission: To provide data and information services for environmental science on behalf of NERC
- People: 35+ staff - mixture of data scientists, software engineers and community engagement experts

External stakeholders

We have a strong network of international partners which has been built over the years via collaborations on research projects and developing innovative data services.

Operations team in meeting room

Building community and supporting collaboration

CF workshop

ELLIE FISHER, ALISON PAMMENT

The CF (Climate and Forecast) Conventions are a community-developed standard for describing Earth system science data in the netCDF data format. The CF Conventions can encode information that describes the coordinate systems, data structure, geophysical meaning and units of each variable, and how the data were collected. It is widely used by weather and climate scientists and remote-sensing researchers and is gaining traction in new communities, such as biogeochemistry and operational weather prediction.

The aim of this workshop was to engage the cross-domain CF community to gather user needs and develop a [high-level CF roadmap](#). Membership of the organising committee for this workshop was diverse, with individuals representing CEDA, the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS), EUMETSAT (European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites), the University of Reading, Unidata (part of the National Science Foundation), NOAA (National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration), and Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), among other institutions.

Over the first two days (Part 1), there were a set of sessions focusing on key themes such as controlled vocabularies and units, metadata for representing statistical uncertainty, metadata for statistical processing, requirements for new technologies, interoperability and cross-domain challenges. Each of these included a keynote and several lightning talks, a format which was designed to stimulate discussion and thought amongst the workshop participants. Speakers were invited from a broad range of CF users and potential users. Memorable presentations from CEDA included Charlotte Pascoe: “Communicating (and understanding) uncertainty through the value chain”, Martin Jukes: “Challenges in the Expanding Scope of the CMIP Data Request”, and Ag Stephens: “Teaching Large Language Models to speak CF-NetCDF”.

Attendees at the 2024 CF Meeting which took place from 17-20 September 2024 at the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) in Norrköping, Sweden.

With the previous two conferences held remotely, we had a blank slate to create an in-person experience (with remote attendance as well). We drew inspiration from past events we had attended, gathered feedback from peers, and focused on building a programme that balanced science talks with practical career development.

What happened on the day

Around 100 people attended the conference in-person and 50 online with attendees from RAL Space, Diamond, National Physical Laboratory (NPL), universities, startups, government, Lockheed Martin, UK Space Agency (UKSA), European Space Agency (ESA), UK Space Command, and more. The day was designed to consist of a mix of contributions from early career attendees and space sector experts in academia, government, and industry. We also wanted to contain both a showcase of the exciting new science in the space sector and address practical soft skills needed for a successful career. The day started with an interactive workshop led by spacecareers.uk focusing on networking and soft skills, a panel discussion on careers in the space sector, and a guest talk about tackling the imposter phenomenon. This was followed by a selection of lightning talks from early career attendees, a poster session, and another panel session on the future of the space sector. Finally, there was a keynote talk by ESA reserve astronaut Meganne Christian.

Conclusion

The day was really well received and it received some very positive feedback from attendees, such as:

“The organisation was great, and it ran very smoothly”

“the sessions were all interesting and I very much enjoyed the day!”

“There was a lovely atmosphere in the rooms”

“The conference was really well organised throughout, from initial calls to logistics and even the presenting technology”

“I particularly enjoyed the lightning talks – it was great to hear the variety of work that is being done by all the attendees and the lessons they have learnt along the way.”

“I thought the day was really well organised and enjoyed all the talks”

We thoroughly enjoyed the experience of organising the conference. Although difficult at times, seeing the event come together on the day was a great feeling and we learnt many new skills throughout the process, which are now being applied at CEDA!

Following the success of this event, the next conference is being planned for late 2025!

Nicola, Molly and Emily speaking during the RAL Space early careers conference.

Nurturing future talent at CEDA

ZACH WHARTON, RORY JENNS

CEDA had the pleasure of welcoming two industrial placement students, Rory Jenns and Zach Wharton, who joined us as Software Engineers for their Industrial Placement year.

Revolutionising CEDA's Data Catalogue

Zach took on the task of developing new front-end features for the [CEDA Data Catalogue](#). Using JavaScript, he introduced an 'embedded search' on catalogue record pages, allowing users to further refine their searches of related content. This was a game-changer. Zach's solution provided a more efficient way to access relevant information, giving users greater control and reducing wait times.

Meanwhile, Rory worked on tagging datasets based on the classifications of their licences by what use they permit. This allowed users to tell if a dataset has a licence for their use (e.g. academic or commercial usage). Rory's changes also provide greater flexibility in access routes to data associated with different licensing options, allowing CEDA to cater for diverse options needed by data providers storing data in the CEDA archive.

Enhancing the Archival of Data

Rory and Zach's paths crossed again when they both worked on crucial systems for ingesting data from users into the archive.

Rory started his placement by improving 'Arrivals', a Python/Django app for reviewing incoming datasets arriving in the archive. He spoke with data scientists at CEDA to find out how they used the system, where improvements could be made, and desired features. Using this knowledge he created web tools that give our data scientists greater visibility and control to review and fix incoming datasets. This allows staff to review datasets directly from their web browsers, lowering the entry barrier.

At the same time, Zach revitalised our 'FileOps server', an internal system that is part of our file processing pipeline. Zach utilised a modern technology called FastAPI to simplify and enhance the system, making it easier to develop and maintain, while also increasing its reliability and capacity to handle a higher volume of requests. This upgrade was a significant milestone for CEDA, ensuring our file operations would continue to be efficient and dependable. Zach's work prepared the 'FileOps server' for future growth and adaptability, maintaining high standards in our file management processes.

Rory and Zach stood behind the RAL Space sign in front of the R100 building on Harwell Campus

Engaging with External Partners

Both Zach and Rory had the chance to engage with some of the big names in environmental data, working with the Met Office and the European Space Agency respectively. Here's what they had to say:

Zach Wharton, Placement Student

“ My standout experience at CEDA is most likely working on a software development project with the Met Office. I was able to advance as a software developer because I collaborated with well-known industry names. It was eye-opening to work with external stakeholders and see the real-world applications of our work.”

Rory Jenns, Placement Student

“ Working on the Data Relay Hub has been a unique experience for me. Luckily, I had the chance to work directly with ESA, an opportunity that few this early in their career receive. In the work itself, I made use of a variety of technologies while working through how to implement an operational system.”

We're incredibly proud of the contributions Rory and Zach have made during their time at CEDA and wish them all the best in their future endeavours. Their hard work and dedication have left a lasting impact, and we're excited to see what they achieve next.

CEDA Operations team in a social space

Developing ESGF's next-generation architecture ready for CMIP7

RHYS EVANS, DAVE POULTER AND PHILIP KERSHAW

The [Coupled Model Intercomparison Project \(CMIP\)](#) is an international climate modelling project run by the World Climate Research Programme, with the goal of understanding the similarities and differences between climate models. It has been running for 20 years through multiple phases, and with CMIP6 coming to the end, plans for CMIP7 have begun.

The Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) was started during CMIP5 with the goal of supporting storage and access of the Peta-scale data produced through CMIP. It provides this through the development, deployment, and maintenance of an open source, globally distributed and federated software infrastructure and tool suite. With the planned phase change in CMIP, the ESGF team, including CEDA, undertook [a major re-evaluation of the system](#) with a view to improve and modernise it. The existing legacy architecture - ESGF '1.0' consists of a set of Nodes distributed across the globe at participating sites. Nodes provide the basic functional unit for a hosting site: a Data Node provides the capability for users to access and download datasets, the Index Node provides a searchable catalogue of all the data held. Index Nodes are synchronised so that any one Index holds a catalogue of all the data held across Data Nodes in the federation.

Following the review of the architecture, much work was accomplished to improve ESGF but one key challenge remained centred on ESGF's search services and the Index Node. The existing system was complicated to maintain and the mechanism to synchronise content between Index Nodes was prone to error. These issues led to nodes often being offline for extended periods of time, and then failing to fully synchronise. Over time the distributed nature of the system resulted in the whole system being degraded.

Working with partners from the DOE-funded ESGF2 project, CEDA developed a new and novel solution and established a core team to implement it. At its heart, an event stream manages the publication of search content. This can be thought of by analogy with a postal service: when data is ready to be published into the search catalogue it is posted into the event stream. Index Nodes listen to the event stream for the arrival of "post" i.e. publication data that has been posted. Once this data is received, they add it to their search catalogues. In this way, it is possible to make a scalable service where participating Index Nodes pick up the same content and are therefore in sync.

Besides the system for publishing the decision was also taken to reduce the number of Index Nodes to two to simplify the overall system: one in the US and one in Europe (CEDA). The addition of an event stream has that added benefit that other services in the federation will now also be able to subscribe to events. This could be used for example to trigger automatic replication of data between nodes meeting a site's predefined criteria. Taken together all of the above innovations have been labelled as ESGF "Next Generation" or version 2.0.

Another issue raised during the review of ESGF's 1.0 architecture was the software maintenance burden for the range of applications and tools it supports. To reduce this effort, it was decided an existing standard for handling metadata should be implemented. The SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs (STAC), designed and developed by and for the Earth Observation community, is a set of JSON schema based around GeoJSON to allow the description and cataloging of data with Geometry and temporal components. STAC's design philosophy is to require a minimal core and then be made more specific to a project through a set of community written extensions. The team decided this could allow it to be adapted for the model data produced by CMIP. This has opened up access to existing software that the STAC community has built and maintained, including an implementation of the STAC API specification and a Python client that allow the user to perform faceted and free text search. This will reduce the maintenance burden on ESGF's development team.

The changes being made should improve the resilience of both the publication and search services for ESGF, and reduce the maintenance requirements for both the service developers and the operations staff running the services. CEDA continues to play an active role in the development of the project as we ramp up to operations for CMIP7 and reception of data from the first model runs from participating modelling centres around the world.

Laura Wilcox with illuminated globe

Net Zero

Sustainable storage
and computing

Net Zero

Sustainable storage and computing

Society's increasing reliance on digital technologies means we must take into consideration the growing environmental, economic and social impacts. These impacts are wide ranging: from energy consumption, to the lifecycle and materials used in the physical hardware of our computers. UKRI has committed to ensuring its digital research infrastructure (e.g. supercomputers like JASMIN) will be net zero by 2040 or sooner.

It is our responsibility to ensure system operations and user practices are as sustainable as possible. In CEDA we have been proactive in seeking opportunities to contribute to reducing environmental impacts, for example through our leadership of the [UKRI NetZero DRI Scoping Study](#), and through development of a JASMIN Sustainability Action Plan.

By actively tackling sustainability issues, we are ensuring the research we are supporting is making the most of the (admittedly high) energy use required for running our digital research infrastructure. We will continue to adapt our ways of working to ensure power usage is optimised, valuable research is encouraged, and decisions (within our control) are made to ensure sustainability is at the forefront of our work.

Example research project:

UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Project - net-zero-dri.ceda.ac.uk

Between 2021-2023, CEDA staff led a consortium of 20 partners to scope out a UKRI roadmap to deliver net zero digital research infrastructure by 2040 or sooner.

Over 150 detailed recommendations were produced, outlined in the [Final Technical Report](#) which has been accessed over 2000 times (as of June 2025). The report provides a full account of evidence collected in the project. It combines detailed technical analysis with a literature survey and results from community and stakeholder engagement activities.

[A follow-on project](#) is now being undertaken by Martin Juckes, who is on secondment as a Visiting Fellow at the University of Oxford Physics Department.

Patrick McGuire in dry grass after a long, hot summer

JASMIN Environmental Sustainability Action Plan

ADRIAN HINES

Environmental sustainability is an increasingly important issue for JASMIN, and poses a challenge due to the inherently energy-intensive nature of any large-scale digital research infrastructure. However, the JASMIN team and the JASMIN user community share a motivation to tackle this challenge by minimising environmental impacts without impeding progress with the scientific projects that JASMIN supports.

A JASMIN Environmental Sustainability Action Plan has been developed, setting out actions that will contribute to reducing the environmental impact of JASMIN over time. This plan draws upon efforts in the wider UKRI community, including the [UKRI Net Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Scoping Study](#) and the [NetDRIVE project](#).

In order to support the development and implementation of the plan, a JASMIN Environmental Sustainability Working Group has been formed. The group comprises JASMIN team members from CEDA and from Scientific Computing. Several of the group members have completed the “Creating a Sustainable STFC” training programme.

Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory Weather Radar

The action plan covers a number of key areas that are within the influence of the JASMIN team and JASMIN user community, specifically:

Monitoring and metrics

Recent work has delivered significant improvements to power usage monitoring systems in place for JASMIN, and the implementation of approximate carbon emissions calculations attributed to elements of the system. In combination with project-level accounting on the new LOTUS2 CPU cluster, and existing monitoring of storage, this provides a pathway to calculating carbon emissions per project. The next steps in our action plan are to continue to improve the accuracy of our power monitoring, to implement and refine project-level carbon emission monitoring, and to work with other digital research infrastructures to encourage comparison and learning.

Procurement

Whilst procurement activities for JASMIN are constrained by government procurement rules and processes, we are working within this framework to ensure that environmental sustainability is considered. We have made two major JASMIN hardware procurements over the last year, both of which have delivered improvements in energy efficiency. Firstly, the CPU cores in the new LOTUS2 cluster are more energy efficient than their predecessors; secondly, the recently purchased new storage comprises solid-state devices, which have considerably lower power consumption than the hard drive storage that they will replace. Energy efficiency will continue to be an important consideration when making procurement decisions.

User practices

With a large user base, the efficiency of use of JASMIN resources by the user community has a big impact on the overall scale of resources that are required to meet the user needs. Improvement in the efficiency of use can reduce pressure to expand capacity, slowing the rate of growth in energy use over time. Influencing user behaviour to improve efficiency is therefore a key activity within the plan. Efforts are underway to encourage group workspace managers to review data holdings, and to take conscious decisions about either removing, or moving inactive data to tape. Alongside this, the opportunity is being taken to require group workspace managers to reduce data volumes in advance of migration of data to new storage. These efforts will relieve pressure on storage capacity.

The next steps fall into two main areas. Firstly, efforts will continue to encourage appropriate choice of storage media, in particular to optimise use of less energy intensive storage. The release of the Near-Line Data Store (see associated article) is an important step in facilitating this. Secondly, we will work with others to develop and deliver training materials that enhance the ability of the JASMIN community to optimise their workflows and code.

Operating practices

Alongside encouraging changes to user behaviour, we are also taking steps to improve the way in which JASMIN is operated to improve energy efficiency. The UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Study looked at the feasibility of reducing energy usage through changes in operation of infrastructure, for example through optimising processor clock speeds, or adopting “green” approaches to job scheduling. We have taken account of these findings when configuring the new LOTUS2 cluster, in particular through implementation of power management, which enables nodes to power down when not in use. We continue to work with the wider community through engagement in the NetDRIVE project.

Net Zero: Increasing the use of tape via the Near Line Data Store

NEIL MASSEY

The volume of data stored in research oriented data centres, including CEDA, is large and increasing year-on-year. The advent of exascale computing and next generation observational systems will exacerbate this, with a predicted exponential increase in the storage capacity required at CEDA.

This data is stored and analysed on data-intensive super computing systems such as JASMIN. Currently, on JASMIN, users access data in two different partitions: their [Group Workspaces \(GWS\)](#) and the CEDA Archive. Both of these are typically stored on a combination of spinning disk and solid state storage. While both the CEDA archive and GWS have access to and provision of tape storage, it is underused, particularly for the GWS. Storing and analysing such huge volumes of data on disk and solid state storage is expensive, from a monetary point of view, as well as having a carbon cost that is in direct opposition to the UK government and research councils' Net-Zero targets. [STFC has a target of being Net-Zero by 2040.](#)

At CEDA and JASMIN, we have long wished for users to utilise the tape provision in a more dynamic way. Ideally, they would use tape in a similar manner to disk, producing data via modelling or observations, storing it on tape only, and then downloading it from tape to disk when they need to analyse it. Previous technical issues have prevented this workflow from being widely adopted by JASMIN users, notably the difficulty in interacting with a tape system interface, the lag between requesting a file from tape and receiving it on the disk, and the difficulty in restarting processes that write to, or read from, tape that have been interrupted part-way through. This has a real impact on scientists' data analysis workflows, causing them to rely on disk, despite its attendant carbon impact.

JASMIN at Centre for Environmental Data Analysis

[The Near-Line Data Store \(NLDS\)](#) presents a solution to these problems, whilst having minimal impact on (or even enhancing) scientific analysis workflows. NLDS is a hierarchical data storage and cataloguing system consisting of a middle layer cache of object storage between disk and tape systems. It presents a user-friendly command line tool and Python library, to upload, download, and search for data, as well as status tracking.

When users upload their files into NLDS, the files are first copied to object storage and catalogued, and then backed up to tape. The use of object storage enables their data to be cloud accessible via a URL, with access control provided by Access Control Lists.

Periodically, data is removed from the object store according to a set of policies designed to have minimal impact on users. These consist of rules such as: “the data must be above a certain size for removal”, and “the data has not been accessed for a long time”. Data is only removed from the object storage as it begins to approach capacity (e.g. 80% used), so some files may never need to be removed. If a file requested for download has been removed from the object store due to these policies, it will first be retrieved from tape to the object store and downloaded from there. NLDS was partially funded by an [EU Horizon Europe¹ grant](#) with the condition that it must be portable and open-source. To this end, NLDS is fully portable and can be installed on any multi-user system that has an S3² - compatible object store and an [xRootD-compatible tape system](#) available over a network. It has been successfully installed on systems ranging in size from a laptop to a supercomputer, via both bare-metal and containerised with Kubernetes deployment.

NLDS presents a new software package to allow dynamic use of tape by users, potentially saving money and carbon emissions. It was made available to JASMIN users in 2025 and represents the pinnacle of almost 4 years’ worth of development at CEDA and JASMIN.

1 NLDS was supported through the ESIWACE2 project. The project ESIWACE2 has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823988.

2 S3 - Simple Storage Service, first developed by Amazon Web Services but it provides a de facto standard API which many third-party object store implementations comply with.

Technical

Tools, expertise
and infrastructure

Technical

Tools, expertise and infrastructure

We focus on delivering robust, user-friendly, and secure data services that support the environmental science community. Our commitment to service resilience and dynamic resource allocation underpins our goal of maintaining 95% uptime, ensuring researchers have reliable access to critical data and tools. We make data analysis more accessible through Jupyter Notebook Servers, a Web-Processing Service, and a suite of Data Access Tools designed to streamline workflows. Security and reliability are at the heart of our operations, with well-written services, adherence to best practices, and the use of code quality tools to maintain high standards. To stay ahead of evolving needs, we implement regular updates, enable seamless integrations, and actively progress any necessary technical migrations (e.g. to Rocky Linux 9), ensuring our infrastructure remains modern and efficient.

JASMIN's birthday

In 2012, an initial 4.5 petabytes of high-performance storage and associated processing capacity was brought online, signalling the 'birth' of JASMIN and revolutionising processing and analysis of environmental science data for years to come by pioneering the model of bring-the-compute-to-the-data in this domain.

Here's what some of our software team have to say:

William Tucker – Senior DevOps Engineer

“Our container-based services are able to cope with higher loads by scaling up or down.”

Daniel Westwood – Software Engineer

“We provide access to multitudes of data through a variety of channels to suit different user needs.”

Matt Pritchard – JASMIN Operations Manager

“Scheduling dedicated maintenance time allows us to push vital updates with minimal disruption to users.”

Dave Poulter – Technical Manager

“We are investing in tools like Backstage to allow us to monitor our entire software estate, to keep quality high, and act quickly on security issues.”

Alex Manning – Research Software Engineer / Operations Support for JASMIN

“The JASMIN notebook service allows our users to get straight into visualising their data – all from the comfort of their web browser.”

Nicola Farmer – Software Engineer

“We catch errors quickly and ensure changes are working properly before deployment by using tests in the Continuous Integration (CI) pipeline.”

Rhys Evans – Software Engineer

“We use Elasticsearch to store metadata for data in our archive. This helps improve discoverability through services like the CEDA Catalogue.”

Ag Stephens – Head of Partnerships

“We are exploring the use of the Large Language Models and other AI techniques to improve how we support users and manage our data.”

JASMIN Update: Migration to Rocky9 & New hardware

MATT PRITCHARD

Keeping JASMIN up-to-date as a high-performance data analysis platform is a constant and challenging task, but essential for many reasons:

- To meet the needs of an evolving community of users, whose compute and storage needs change with science priorities and new advances in technology
- To keep the operation of JASMIN affordable in terms of operating costs and staff effort
- To keep within constraints of available machine room space, cooling and energy availability and cost
- To keep the platform efficient and secure in a changing world of cybersecurity

With these and many other factors in mind, the JASMIN team works hard behind the scenes to plan improvements and upgrades whilst minimising disruption to users where possible.

This year we targeted the following areas for essential improvements: an operating system upgrade and an exciting new compute cluster.

Operating system upgrade

Every system relies on an operating system, whether it's a virtual machine, data transfer server, compute node in a cluster, [or even a containerised service](#). Software packages used by these services have to be kept up to date regularly to ensure they are robust against cyber threats, and doing that efficiently across a platform like JASMIN means sourcing updates from automated channels. These are only available for supported versions of operating systems. Eventually, operating systems like CentOS7 reach their "end of life" and need to be replaced. This happens once every few years and needs to be coordinated with teams across STFC, as JASMIN relies on many services which are operated elsewhere within the organisation.

[This year we upgraded our operating system](#), replacing our old system - CentOS7, with Rocky Linux 9. Its end-of-life is May 2032, so we don't anticipate another change for a few years now. The task of updating machine services is not as simple as pressing "update" however. Lower-level software components (such as driver software for network cards, or for connecting to storage systems) are sensitive to specific versions of operating systems, so the choice and implementation of an upgrade is a major undertaking for a platform as complex as JASMIN. While decommissioning services running CentOS7, we replaced them with containerised services where possible (these are easier to update in the future), or with new hosts running Rocky Linux 9. There are inevitably some changes to the look and feel of some services, but a great deal of planning goes into making the transition for users as painless as possible (which we appreciate does not mean pain-free!).

New cluster

An exciting development announced in mid-2024 was the [replacement of JASMIN's CentOS7-based LOTUS cluster with a new 55,000-core cluster](#), tripling compute capacity and moving to new versions of both the operating system (Rocky Linux 9) and the Slurm scheduler. As well as providing a boost in the compute power available to the user community, this brings new capabilities such as automated power-down of idle nodes to save energy. The new cluster and the new configuration designed for it will also enable tracking of compute usage by project. This is important information needed in order to understand and manage compute and energy usage across the platform.

CEDA Accounts portal upgrades

WILLIAM TUCKER

This year, CEDA has completed a series of internal projects to modernise our user account management systems, including upgrading the underlying database technology for enhanced security, implementing a completely new dataset sign-up portal, and improving the look and feel of our user-facing web services such as the registration and account management web pages.

This work marks a major step forward in the reliability, usability, and maintainability of several of CEDA's core systems. It was conducted in response to growing issues with our legacy systems that were burdening support and technical staff, as well as degrading user experience. This also presented an opportunity to retire systems that were built on outdated, unsupported software that may pose security risks if carried forward any longer.

Considerable time was invested in assessing the impact of removing or upgrading long-standing legacy systems, which were often relied upon by modern infrastructure. Strategic upgrades were made in collaboration across expertise within the team to minimise disruption for users. We explored many different approaches to the problem, and settled on solutions only if they met both our user-facing and technical requirements.

The core of the new system is Keycloak, an industry standard and well-supported open-source identity and access management framework. Keycloak was chosen for its extensibility, active community support, and strong alignment with industry best practices. By adopting this framework, we have aligned our user management with up-to-date authentication standards. This has improved our ability to protect user accounts, prevent misuse of our services, and deliver data to users and downstream applications through more secure data download endpoints. For instance, we are now using the OpenID Connect authentication protocol to give users an easier way to download our data with tokens in scripts which act on the user's behalf to fetch data from us. This functionality is being used to support important projects, and we're continually exploring new applications. One example is its planned integration in the next phase of the Earth Observation Data Hub.

From a user's perspective, the front end has been significantly improved, with simpler, more accessible interfaces that make account management and sign-in easier. These changes were informed by feedback from users and aim to reduce friction across a range of common interactions.

Importantly, the new foundation also supports future developments. Keycloak's modular design has allowed us to newly automate parts of our internal workflow and improve interoperability with other parts of our infrastructure through OAuth2 and single-sign-on. An example of this is the recent release of our new CEDA services portal, which builds on the new authentication system to provide a streamlined mechanism for users to register for access to datasets. Dataset approvals, and the addition of new datasets and services to the portal are now much simpler and more automated than before. Overall, the user experience of signing up for an account and applying for access to data is a much more cohesive and accessible process, and we've simultaneously reduced the CEDA staff time needed to manage this process.

In summary, the completion of this project marks a substantial and necessary upgrade to CEDA's core infrastructure. It resolves long-standing technical debt, provides an improved experience for users, enables new functionality and interoperability for our critical services, and creates a reliable and extensible foundation for future development.

Co-create

User centred design,
co-creation and collaboration

Co-create

User centred design, co-creation and collaboration

User-centred design, co-creation, and collaboration are fundamental to delivering services that truly meet the needs of the environmental science community. By actively engaging with users throughout the development process, we ensure our tools and platforms are intuitive, relevant, and impactful. Co-creation allows us to harness the expertise of researchers, data providers, and technical specialists, leading to solutions that are both innovative and grounded in real-world use cases. We build strong partnerships that foster trust, encourage shared learning, and drive continuous improvement. This inclusive approach not only enhances the usability and effectiveness of our services but also ensures they evolve in step with the community’s changing needs.

What is user-centred design?

User centred design is when people, who create new or improve existing processes and services, use an iterative approach that focuses on the needs of the users. These needs are included throughout the design process. This allows the item to be created in the most useful and meaningful way to the person who will be using it.

Why is this important?

We want to create and run great services. To do this efficiently, we must understand who our users are and what they need.

Who are our core communities?

- Peers who are doing similar things to us e.g. staff from other data centres or computing infrastructures
- Researchers using our data and services. The research domains and reasons for using our data are incredibly diverse

Who are our users?
A pie chart showing CEDA Archive users by domain.

What is the data we host being used for? A word cloud showing common words from applications to restricted datasets - prominent words include; rainfall, climate, weather, model, phd, wind, water.

At the CEDA 30th event, we asked attendees to help ‘Co-create our future success’ and asked how we could improve our services from their perspectives. We based these conversations around 14 categories from the [Service Standard](#) - a framework to help government teams create and run great public services:

- Understand users and their needs
- Solve a whole problem for users
- Provide a joined up experience across all channels
- Make the service simple to use
- Make sure everyone can use the service
- Have a multidisciplinary team
- Use agile ways of working
- Iterate and improve frequently
- Create a secure service which protects users’ privacy
- Define what success looks like and publish performance data
- Choose the right tools and technology
- Make new source code open
- Use and contribute to open standards, common components and patterns
- Operate a reliable service

CEDA 30 years celebration day

User centred approaches for environmental data services

POPPY TOWNSEND

Ensuring our data services are fit for purpose is becoming more important as a broader range of people find and access environmental data. User centred approaches help achieve this by tailoring services to diverse needs and enhancing communication of complex science.

We have created a [‘user-centred design toolkit for environmental services’](#) with the aim of supporting data, software and design experts to create user-friendly and effective environmental data services. This toolkit provides a range of resources, case studies and guidance needed to collaborate with users, gather insights, and co-design solutions that work.

The toolkit was shaped by collaborations across all environmental science domains, with a range of experts in design, data management, communications and engagement, and software engineering.

The toolkit was created as part of the NERC BOOST-EDS project; the user-centred aspect of the project was led by CEDA staff and is [summarised in this report](#).

Our journey towards becoming a truly user centred organisation is only just beginning. Our current guiding principles for embedding user centred approaches across our organisation are:

- **Listen and adapt:** we must understand diverse perspectives and redefine solutions to suit their needs
- **One size does not fit all:** use multiple customised methods (surveys, interviews, workshops) to get the information we need
- **Prioritise and facilitate:** we must carefully design and facilitate user centred approaches to ensure inclusivity and participation
- **Collaborate, share and disseminate:** it is an iterative process, we should share the highs and lows so others can benefit

We’ve identified three key themes for future work:

- **People and communities:** we must foster a collaborative environment and build a network for sharing challenges and successes
- **Processes, governance, and strategy:** we must operationalise findings, embed user centred approaches in strategy, and explore creative methods for undertaking new work in difficult financial landscapes
- **Information management:** ensure unrestricted access to project documents and resources to promote transparent collaborations and reduce duplication

WHAT ARE USER CENTRED APPROACHES?

- An iterative approach that prioritises end-user needs, preferences, and experiences throughout design and development
- While known by various names (such as user experience, user research, user interface design, user acceptance testing, co-creation, co-design), we use the broader term ‘user centred approach’ to broadly cover all work in this area, focussing always on the user’s perspective

The [Nielsen Norman Group](#), a globally trusted team of user experience experts, state there are six levels of maturity for embedding user centred approaches within organisations (see figure).

The six levels of user experience maturity, as defined by the [Nielsen Norman Group](#). The NERC EDS, which CEDA is part of, is moving from Level 2 to 3 as a direct result of this work.

Ralph Burton working on computer models

From code to canvas: bringing climate data to life

AUTHOR: POPPY TOWNSEND

The warming stripes are a simple visual way to represent our planet's changing climate - with each stripe representing the temperature of a single year. A [new tool has been created](#) to allow anyone to produce a personalised climate stripe for any location – whether that's for your hometown, workplace, or favourite holiday destination. This tool can be [used for public engagement activities](#).

Talking about our changing climate is one of the most powerful ways we can encourage positive change. The original stripes were created by climate scientist, [Ed Hawkins](#) (National Centre for Atmospheric Science and University of Reading), and have been [used many times across the world](#) to inspire conversations. The red colours indicate warmer temperatures, whereas the blue colours indicate cooler temperatures.

The [show your stripes website](#) provides an image file for well-known locations across the world. It is purposely simple. The images are widely used but the code to create the images is not publicly available. Climate data is also extremely complicated to navigate for non-expert users but is increasingly required for non-traditional uses such as craft activities (see the image below for a real helpdesk message we received).

Thank you for getting back to me. I think the problem lies with me as I rely totally on voice over technology (as I am sight impaired) to search the web. Your site is very comprehensive and so for me to listen to all the options and then remember where they were is tricky.

I am so pleased you are happy to help me. It is a bit of a crazy reason why I want the data. So excuse the lack of science! It is my sisters 60th birthday on the 25th July of this year. I want to knit her a temperature scarf for each of her 60 years.

We created a new tool for generating personalised UK-based warming stripes, with the idea being people could use them for their own craft projects at home. The tool [uses a dataset in our Archive called HadUK-Grid](#) - provided by the UK Met Office, this freely available dataset is based on observations from the UK's land network of weather stations, [interpolated onto a uniform grid](#) to provide complete coverage across the UK.

A second version of the tool allows for generating warming stripes anywhere in the world using [high resolution gridded climate data in our Archive](#) provided by the Climatic Research Unit (CRU).

Using the tool for public engagement

At the end of June 2024, over 2,000 teachers and students and 10,000 visitors descended onto the Harwell Campus. It was a huge celebration and showcase of [everything we do at RAL](#), our sister sites and with our partners around the world.

CEDA designed and delivered an activity to co-create a climate mosaic. The tool was fundamental in enabling the artwork to be based on real temperature data for Harwell, Oxfordshire. The finished climate mosaic consisted of two artworks – each measuring 3.5 metres by 0.5 metre – each piece visualising data over several generations (100+ years).

Hundreds, if not thousands, of people contributed to the artwork – which is now on display in the STFC Visitor Centre at Harwell Campus.

Families glueing on tiles to create the final climate mosaic during Harwell Open Week

Changing the world with Complex Citations

CHARLOTTE PASCOE, MOLLY MACRAE, GRAHAM PARTON

Climate data has a story: it is created by climate models, generated by instrument measurements and then put into archives to be used by all sorts of scientists. A climate dataset can contribute to many different science outputs and a science output can be based on many different climate datasets. This work uses a novel approach to citation to tell the story of scientific data: Where is the data used? Where did the data come from?

CEDA worked with the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) to publish the data presented in the plots of the [IPCC WGI Sixth Assessment Report \(AR6\)](#). Our new work on citations, which also includes the Research Data Alliance (RDA), enables us to concisely explain the details of the input climate model simulations used to make those IPCC plots. Concision is important here because the IPCC plots present statistics that are drawn from many hundreds of climate datasets. Our method puts information about all of these datasets into a single Complex Citation. The information in a complex citation is carefully structured so that it can be used to give credit to all of the producers of the data, and also show the way to the many individual datasets that were used.

We collaborated with our IPCC Data Distribution Centre colleagues at the German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ) in a pilot implementation for complex citations. Together we published complex citations using Zenodo to connect 107 IPCC AR6 plots to their [CMIP6 climate model input datasets](#). The pilot complex citations contained both a machine-readable json-LD metadata file (following [schema.org](#)) for automated access, and a spreadsheet CSV file for people to inspect. A complex citation is a node in the landscape of DOIs. In our pilot, the complex citation represents the missing stepping stone in the path of provenance from IPCC to CMIP6.

With complex citations, everyone from YouTubers to ministers of state can find out the exact sources of the data being presented to them and whether it is from a place that they can trust. With complex citations, climate modelling centres will be able to demonstrate the impact of their work by pointing to the many and various science outputs that use it. And with complex citations, AI can declare the data sources used to generate responses.

Figure showcasing how complex citations are constructed using the CMIP6 citation service

Outreach

Public engagement and education

Outreach

Public engagement and education

Public engagement and outreach are vital to our mission of making environmental data accessible, meaningful, and impactful. By connecting with diverse audiences - from school students to international researchers - we help demystify data science, inspire future generations, and foster a deeper understanding of environmental challenges and solutions.

In the past year, CEDA has led and contributed to a wide range of outreach initiatives. During Harwell Open Week, we developed interactive activities including a [climate-themed mosaic artwork](#), a data-driven escape room challenge, and support for [a butterfly data exhibit using JASMIN](#). During the week we also ran a coding workshop and hosted a dedicated CEDA stand. Our involvement also extended to STEM fairs (e.g. Durham and Leeds), where early career staff engaged with students, and representation at Farnborough International Airshow, where we contributed to the [Pioneers of Tomorrow blog](#). We’ve also supported space-themed storytelling and delivered STEM careers talks at local schools.

Our collaboration with the Engineering Education Project (EEP) has been especially impactful, involving sixth-form students in real-world engineering challenges, including Arduino/C++ workshops, prototype development, and poster presentations. We also contributed to Supercomputing 2024 in Atlanta by gathering user stories and creating slides on JASMIN research. Other highlights include the [CEDA 30th anniversary event](#), the [SmolAgents tech blog](#), and a dedicated JASMIN stand at [Computing Insights UK](#) in Manchester.

What makes a great engagement activity?

From Harwell to Home: Takeaway science resources to extend the HOW experience

DANIEL WESTWOOD

During my second year of the graduate programme at STFC I undertook a six week placement with the Public Engagement (PE) office, with the aim of collecting and preparing teaching resources for participants of the Harwell Open Week (HOW) so that they could continue their learning at home. The Harwell Open Week 2024 was an event that took place on the STFC campus from Monday to Saturday 29th June and consisted of various school and stakeholder visitors attending tours, workshops and sessions. The focal point was the public open day on Saturday, which saw several thousand public visitors across all ages and backgrounds.

In considering possible placements, I had a strong desire to get more involved with public engagement at STFC, as I had taken part in specific events in the past such as Stargazing and the Engineering Experiences Programme. I contacted Sophy Palmer, head of the PE Team, in early 2024 to find out more about how I could participate specifically with the Open Week, with a particular desired outcome: to extend learning opportunities beyond the scope of just the week itself.

I started my placement in mid-April, when planning and organisation for the event was in full swing. I then spent several weeks collecting hundreds of video links, documents, activities, workshops and more, from various websites across STFC, UKRI, and other external partner organisations. These were organised in relation to the themes of the open week: **Space, Computing, Environment, Nanoscale, Engineering, Health and History**, which were expanded with subtitles as the planning for the event continued. I also added two sections to my resource collection around the site and facilities at **Harwell Campus**, and **STEM learning** beyond STFC. This included a considerable number of existing resources that covered multiple HOW themes, involving topics such as career and skills development.

Throughout my placement, I discovered a vast breadth of resources available across various sites and collections that had not previously been pulled together to such an extent in one place. I also had the opportunity to develop a few new resources, related to my areas of interest, including Environmental Data and Coding. These resources remain available through the [Harwell Open Week website](#), which will be maintained for several years, providing interested members of the public a wide range of learning opportunities in their own homes.

Visitors on site at RAL exploring the campus during Harwell Open Week in June 2024

Daniel Westwood, Placement Student

“ Overall, the Harwell Open Week was a tremendous success for the public engagement team. Months of logistical planning and organisation culminated in a day packed with activities to suit all audiences and age ranges. On the public day, I was involved in the RAL Space escape room, Mission Phoenix – an amazing experience featuring a briefing from ESA Reserve Astronaut Meganne Christian. I was able to see firsthand the excitement and enthusiasm showcased by everyone involved, and the impact on the general public who took part throughout the day.”

Accompanying various signage around the event were QR codes advertising the website for the Open Week, as well as the learning resources available directly through the website that had been put together. Seeing people engage with the material I had created – either during the public day or by saving the link for when they returned home – was an extremely rewarding experience.

After the Open Week, the Public Engagement team let me know that the resources I had collected would continue to be hosted on the HOW website, as well as for the National Labs Public Engagement (NLPE) Resource Collection. This project is in development involving members of the STFC public engagement team, and I will continue to converse with and assist the PE team in this endeavour and future outreach projects.

Students at University of Oxford Physics

Bytes and blazes: teaching data science via Mission Phoenix

POPPY TOWNSEND, JESSE ALEXANDER

In June 2024, for the first time in nine years, Harwell Science and Innovation Campus opened its doors to 2,000 school children and over 10,000 members of the public – offering a rare opportunity to experience world-class science and facilities up close. This was dubbed Harwell Open Week (HOW). In addition to welcoming visitors to our laboratories and space test facilities, RAL Space ran Mission Phoenix, an escape-room-style activity for schools and the public. CEDA staff were instrumental in co-designing and delivering this activity to show the importance of data science.

Set on the fictional Ember Island that faces recurring wildfires, Mission Phoenix challenged teams to complete tasks designed to help bring residents to safety. From suiting up in clean room gear, to using infrared cameras to detect heat sources, and analysing real satellite images, each task brings participants closer to the mission's goal: preparing a new satellite that will keep a watchful eye over Ember Island to monitor future wildfires.

CEDA staff designed two tasks to showcase the work that we do: 'data storage' and 'data transfer'. In the 'data storage' activity, the staff introduced themselves as a data scientists who make sure that the satellite data has no bugs or errors. Basic data management concepts were introduced; teams were asked to sort through the environmental data files (soft play balls) to find and remove the bad data (e.g. broken balls, balls labelled with irrelevant information such as cat videos). This enabled the information shared via the supercomputer (tube) to be clear and accurate to send to scientists, and of better quality.

The 'data transfer' activity involved a software engineer, who enables the transfer of data. The activity mimicked how packets of data move from one location to another, giving the example of Sentinel satellites which transfer Earth observation images to different data centres globally via a ground station on Earth. For this task, teams had to stand within a ladder shape on the floor and transfer data (toy cushions) by passing the packet from one person to the next until it reached its destination. They had to make sure to follow the rules according to each data packet, such as 'pass using only your left hand' which showed how data packets have instructions attached to them which direct them to the right place.

As teams progressed through the tasks, they pieced together a map revealing wildfire locations and data about the harmful smoke, helping them to chart a safe evacuation route for a school on the island. Mission Phoenix showcased the breadth of work behind real space missions, highlighted the tangible impacts of Earth observation, and allowed visitors to meet and engage with staff from across RAL Space – increasing awareness of a wide range of career opportunities.

Kids dropping suitable data types (balls) into our data storage facility JASMIN (tube) during RAL Space's Mission Phoenix

RAL Space staff members in the space-themed escape room Mission Phoenix which ran during Harwell Open Week in June 2024

Future Goals

Environmental Data Service

The NERC Environmental Data Service provides a focal point for environmental scientific data and information – via a network of distributed data centres (CEDA being one of them), with domain-specific expertise. Our role is to tackle a fundamental paradox; we have more environmental data than ever before, yet accessing and using this wealth of information remains frustratingly difficult. Future work will focus on shaping the future of AI-ready, user-driven environmental data services.

EO DataHub

The EO DataHub is a first of its kind dedicated Earth observation data platform for the UK's needs. As it reaches the end of the initial pathfinder phase of development, NCEO will continue to head this programme with leadership from CEDA and Leicester University and bring the service into full operation for the user community.

Delivery data infrastructure to support the IPCC's next climate assessments

Over the last five years CEDA together with international partners has been leading work to rearchitect and reengineer Earth System Grid Federation. ESGF plays a crucial role to the [WCRP](#) providing the data infrastructure to make available climate projections outputs from modelling centres around the world for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project. Analysis of CMIP data feeds directly into the IPCC's assessment reports on climate change. We have an immediate goal to support the next phase of CMIP, CMIP7 in which CEDA will provide one of two major hubs for data discovery and access - ESGF-East together with ESGF-West hosted by US partners.

AI

We will explore various techniques (such as Retrieval Augmented Generation, RAG) to build trustworthy chatbots informed by CEDA/JASMIN documentation. Expand our training and documentation to support JASMIN users in building efficient Machine Learning pipelines. Continue to engage with partners across NERC, STFC and beyond, to identify and explore the use of ML and AI methods to improve our services and support for user communities.

JASMIN

Invest in new 35PB SSD storage which will partially replace old capacity and should significantly reduce machine room space & power consumption. Further investment is needed to secure additional storage and cater for any required increase in capacity. This is essential to support the continued growth of the CEDA Archive, CMIP7, ARIA and other new programmes.

We are also aiming for the Near-Line Data Store (NLDS) service to become a key storage component in user workflows, enabling the use of lower-energy storage for all users. Increasing the use of JASMIN for 3rd-party training and hackathon events and balancing stronger controls with user requirements for improved access & performance in the evolving cybersecurity landscape.

JASMIN at Centre for Environmental
Data Analysis

Metrics, Finance, Projects and Outputs

JENIFFER BULPETT

CEDA's key goal is to ensure that we are providing the best possible service to our user communities to enable cutting-edge environmental science research. Earlier sections have highlighted some of our key achievements, projects we've supported, and challenges we have overcome this year. This final section presents usage metrics, financial and project details, and our outputs—publications, talks, posters, and training delivered in 2024-2025.

Summary and usage information

CEDA exists to support the atmospheric, Earth observation, and near-Earth environment research communities in the UK and globally through the provision of data management and access services. CEDA enhances this role through the development and maintenance of tools and services to aid data preservation, curation, discovery and visualisation; all of which add value for the worldwide user community.

The JASMIN data analysis facility provides petascale data-compute capabilities for the UK and wider environmental research communities. This section of the annual report presents summaries of CEDA Archive and JASMIN usage.

Data Archive Service

CEDA delivers Data Archive services for the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS), the National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO), and the NERC/STFC-funded UK Solar System Data Centre (UKSSDC), as part of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

Data Curation

258 new datasets have been created and made available via the [CEDA catalogue](#) - bringing the total number of published datasets to 9272 (as of Apr 2025). 124 new DOIs were issued in this period, bringing the number of DOled resources to 1054 (as of Apr 2025).

Annual CEDA Archive Deposits: April 2024 to March 2025

Total volume deposited	3.0 Petabytes
Total number of files deposited	26,259,789

Usage of CEDA Data

Annual CEDA Archive Usage: April 2024 to March 2025

Total number of users/distinct IP addresses	110,177
Total data downloaded	1.93 Petabytes
Total number of files downloaded	132,925,688
Number of datasets with downloads	7,598

Table: Summary figures for usage by CEDA consumers during the reporting year

	New users period 2024-25	5-year period 2019-24
Registrations	9,145	48,200
% new users from the UK	45%	50%
% new users in Universities	67%	63%

Table: New registered users statistics for the reporting year and preceding 5-year period.

Usage of JASMIN

JASMIN delivers analysis and compute capability for the environmental science community, predominantly for NCAS and NCEO, but also supports other NERC domains: oceanography, polar science, geology and earth sciences, ecology and hydrology.

As of March 2025 there are:

- Approximately 2200 active JASMIN users
- Over 450 shared group workspaces, with 29 Petabytes of storage allocated to them.
- Approximately 35 tenancies in the JASMIN community cloud

General overview

Supporting our users

There were 5515 queries received by the helpdesk over this period (covering both CEDA Archive and JASMIN services). These queries cover all aspects of data support except dataset/service applications or long-term data management discussions.

Over 1000 applications were processed for access to restricted datasets.

Collaborations

CEDA works closely with STFC's [Scientific Computing Department](#) to deliver the JASMIN infrastructure.

In 2024/2025, significant national and international collaborations have continued to support the international climate modelling community, Earth Observation and atmospheric research. On the national scale, CEDA itself reflects a collaboration between the earth observation community, the atmospheric sciences community (via [NCEO](#) and [NCAS](#)), and the space weather community.

Additionally, CEDA is:

1. Working closely with the other NERC Environmental Data Centres, as part of the [NERC Environmental Data Service](#).
2. Leading, developing and operating the Earth System Grid Federation ([ESGF](#)) in support of the seventh Coupled Model Intercomparison Project ([CMIP](#)). CEDA and ORNL co-lead the ESGF Technical leadership group and partner with a global network of climate data service providers, including the European ENES community and US and Australian research organisations.
3. Working with the wider UK atmospheric science and earth observation communities, via a range of projects, with [NCAS](#) and other [NERC](#) funding.
4. Working with the European Space Agency on projects such as the [ESA](#) Climate Change Initiative ([CCI](#)) and the Knowledge Exchange and Climate Modelling User Group (CMUG) project.
5. Delivering part of the UK Collaborative Ground Segment for Sentinel data (with [UK Space Agency](#), [Airbus](#), [Satellite Applications Catapult](#)) with the role to provide Sentinel data mirror archives and data processing capability for the UK academic community.

6. Operating a Data Hub Relay (DHR) on behalf of ESA as a fully functioning member of the ESA DHR network. This supports CEDA use of this for Copernicus data retrievals for the CEDA Mirror Archive.
7. Representing the UK internationally on the inter-space agency CEOS data group (WGISS). CEDA lead the Jupyter Notebooks topic publishing the BEST practice in January 2025, additionally bringing the work to new NERC communities via the BOOST projects, giving two presentations, and attending the two CEOS plenaries remotely.
8. Working with [ECMWF](#) to provide EO scientists with the high-resolution atmospheric analyses they need to process satellite observations. Providing access to ERA5 products to aid wider EO and atmospheric research use.
9. Disseminating climate and weather data to the research community, by working with colleagues in the [UK Met Office](#). Additionally, aiding open access to key Met Office datasets, including those supporting the UK State of the Climate reports.
10. Supporting the [Climate and Forecast Metadata \(CF\) Conventions](#) with partners in [University of Reading](#), [UK Met Office](#), and multiple US research institutions.
11. Working with the [CMIP Panel](#), the [WGCM Infrastructure Panel](#), and a range of CMIP Task Forces to develop the collaborative framework for the next phase of CMIP and with the [IPCC Task Group on Data \(TG-DATA\)](#) to ensure transparency and clear lines of provenance for data cited in the IPCC Assessment Reports.
12. Working with the [Research Data Alliance](#) to develop and advance FAIR data standards, research data management practices, and career pathways.
13. Working with [Climateurope2](#) to build a community of practice for the standardisation and support of equitable, quality-assured climate services for society.
14. Supporting Obs4MIPS through a member on the steering panel.
15. Supporting the [GEO initiative](#) and [CEOS BIOMASS](#) through the ground validation archive we created with Matt Disney on the CEDA archive.
16. Supporting the ESA Living Planet Symposium by participating in the program committee and providing abstract reviews.

Funding

In addition to supporting NCAS and NCEO, CEDA also delivers major projects with funding from a range of other bodies, including work for the European Space Agency ([ESA](#)), [DSIT](#), UKSA, and others, as well as participating and coordinating major European projects.

Financial Year	14-15	15-16	16-17	17-18	18-19	19-20	20-21	21-22	22-23	23-24	24-25
NCAS income	829	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	813	1184	1274
NCEO income	390	393	393	393	402	393	418	393	396	408	419
Other NERC income	600	621	825	816	733	883	784	1371	1789	1663	1853
Other income	1394	1505	1092	1280	1458	1377	1476	1391	1590	1755	1415
Total income	3213	3327	3118	3297	3401	3461	3486	3963	4588	5010	4961

Table: Overall funding for CEDA for financial years 2014/15 to 2024/25 (in £k)

Most of this funding comes to CEDA via contracts with NCAS and NCEO, with some via a service level agreement (SLA) between NERC and STFC.

Externally funded projects

The table below shows CEDA's externally funded projects which were active during the reporting year.

Name	Description	Funder	Start date	End date	Value (£k)
EO DataHub	Collaborative project involving public sector and industry partners to develop a UK digital infrastructure for the exploitation of Earth Observation data to support industry, public sector, and the research community	DSIT	01/02/2023	31/03/2025	9,931 (Actual budget for CEDA Staff: 1,016)
ESA CCI Knowledge Exchange	Data archive for ESA Climate Change Initiative as part of wider activity including outreach and education	ESA	5/9/2019	29/08/2024	763.8
ESA Climate Space Knowledge Exchange	Data archive for ESA Climate Change Initiative as part of wider activity including outreach and education	ESA	01/10/2024	31/10/2027	552.2
ESA Data Hub Relay	Operation of a Sentinel Data Hub Relay for ESA	ESA	01/04/2021	31/03/2026	1,141.1
MOHC Data Pipeline 2024-2027	Continuation of the MOHC Data Pipeline that supports the transfer, cataloguing, publication and dissemination of the Met Office Hadley Centre climate simulations	Met Office	01/04/2024	31/03/2027	590
NetDRIVE	Network for sustainable Digital Research Infrastructure Vision and Expertise (NetDRIVE) has been set up to provide a forum for managers, software engineers, academics and others to come together to build a common vision for a sustainable future and to incite a transition to sustainable working practices in the Digital Research Infrastructure communities.	UKRI	01/07/2024	14/02/2025	17.6
NetDRIVE2		UKRI	09/01/2025	31/03/2028	231.7
CCI Obs4MIPS CMUG Phase2	Involvement in reporting on future requirements for the evolution of Obs4MIPs	ESA	01/04/2022	31/08/2026	48.8
ClimatEurope2	Horizon Europe project on standards for climate services	EC	01/09/2022	28/02/27	88
EOEPCA Op Uptake Support	Deploying EOEPCA software onto JASMIN to make CEDA data available to EOEPCA	ESA	01/07/2022	30/06/2024	64.5
Horizon EERIE Data Services	Data Management and Publication for European Eddy-Rich Earth-System models	EC	01/03/2023	31/12/2026	112.8

Name	Description	Funder	Start date	End date	Value (£k)
JASMIN for CCI+ Lakes 22-25	Funding for the use of JASMIN resources for CCI+ Lakes	ESA via the University of Reading	01/04/2023	31/03/2025	16.6
EPOC	The JASMIN platform is being used by EPOC (improving our understanding of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC)) to store and analyse the new experiments, and to allow the UK experiments to be shared with international project partners.	UKRI via the University of Reading	01/04/2022	01/05/2027	111.9
WCRP Hackathon	CEDA/JASMIN support for a Hackathon on data preparation and analysis of climate model data from various models, generated by the Met Office and other organisations.	Met Office	13/12/2024	31/03/2025	18.6

Table: Externally funded projects with a value greater than £15k for 2024/25 (non-core NERC)

Awards & Publications 2024–2025

Awards

A massive congratulations to Alison Pamment and Ellie Fisher, who received the [American Geophysical Union \(AGU\) Open Science Recognition Prize](#) for being major contributors to the CF Conventions and their “global impact in fostering transparency, collaboration, and accessibility in climate and geoscience data”.

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Training and Events

All events run or supported by CEDA are shown below - for further information, [check out the events page on our website](#).

JASMIN Beginners Workshop

This event is a 1-day, hands-on, beginner's training workshop for users of JASMIN. It is aimed at novice to intermediate users who wish to further their JASMIN knowledge.

28th November 2024: Online event, registration open to all, 50 participants

26th February 2025: Face-to-face event, Leeds, registration open to all, 23 participants

JASMIN webinar on new system developments and Near Line Data Store

26th March 2025: 82 attendees

Introduction to JASMIN

24th October 2024: Bespoke support to the first student cohort of the IE CDT (Intelligent Earth Centre for Doctoral Training) at Oxford University in preparation for practical work on JASMIN, 25 students

Introduction to Scientific Computing course

4th November 2024: Module 1 (virtual) Introduction to the bash shell (Unix/Linux), 12 participants

18th - 20th November 2024, 2.5 days: Module 2 (Leeds) Introduction to Python Programming (includes Introduction to software version control with Git and GitHub), 10 participants

20th - 22nd November 2024, 2.5 days: Module 3 (Leeds) Python: Working with Data, 14 participants

Providing JASMIN Training Accounts & Event Support

27th - 31st January 2025: CANARI (Climate Change in the Arctic and North Atlantic Region and Impacts on the UK) research programme sprint week, 60 participants accessed the JASMIN notebook service using training accounts

11th March 2025: REF (Rapid Evaluation Framework for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, phase 7 (CMIP7)) hackathon at the Met office, 5 participants

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Data Analysis**
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL